

LIFE SKILL EDUCATION FOR SELF-MANAGEMENT IN COMPETITIVE WORLD

Kalikumar Das & Dr. Kalipada Das

Lecturer in Education, SCS Autonomous College, Puri (Odisha)

Email Id: kalikumardas008@gmail.com

Teacher in science, Govt. (SSD) High school, Dahapania, Bhadrak (Odisha)

E mail id : kalipadas85@gmail.com

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What are Life Skills ?

According to WHO "Life Skills are abilities for adaptive and positive behavior that enable Individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life."

UNICEF lists ten core life skills which are most important. These are

1. Self Awareness
2. Empathy
3. Effective Communications
4. Inter-personel Relationship
5. Creative Thinking
6. Critical Thinking
7. Problem Soiving
8. Decission Making
9. Coping with Emotions
10. Coping with Stress

Importance of Life Skills

1. Life skills are generic skills.
2. They play important role throughout life.
3. Life skills should also be applied in the context of typical risk situations.
4. Life skills may be directed towards personal actions towards others.
5. They may be directed to change the surrounding environment to make it conducive .

6. They are needed for creating demand and effectively utilizing the existing services.
7. Life skills are need to enhance in order to meet the challenges of life.
8. They are need to help people make informed decision communicate effectively.
9. Life skills develop coping and self management skills to lead a healthy and productive life.

Need of Life Skill Education

Life skill education is designed in addition to other things to promot protective factors and reduce the impact of “risk” factors by improving decision making and focusing on appropriate choices . In school setting, late childhood and adolescence are critical moments of opertunity for building skills and positive habits. During this time children are developing the ability to think abstractly to understand the consequences to relate to their peers in new ways and to solve problems as they experience more independence from parents and develop greater control over their won lives . Developing attitudes,values,skills and competencies is recognized as critical to the development of a child’s sense of self management.

Different Forms of Life Skills

Communication Skills

Use reading,writing and verbal skills to organize and communicate ideas and information.

Analytical Skills

Use of numerical and mathematical concepts,logical reasonings,principles of silence,information analysis,ethical reasonings to make effective decisions and solve problems.

Group Effectiveness Skills

Apply social interaction skills to develop positive relationships and to work effectively with family,community groups and co-workers.

Critical Thinking and Problem Solving

Develop a higher level of concentration, deeper analytical abilities and improve thought processing.

Collaboration Skills

Develop a sprit of work together in our civic and workforce lives for meaningful and effective results.

Creativity and Innovation Skills

Develop innovative capacity and a creative sprit for personal and professional success.

Personal Management Skill

Develop self-sufficiency and responsibility for effectiveness in personal and occupational life.

How Life Skill Education is Helpful in Self-Management?

Life Skill education-

1. Develops “emotional Intelligence “and skills for managing emotions and inter personal relations.
2. Positively influence the mediators of problem behaviours.
3. Have an impact on multiple adolescent health and development needs.
4. Develop social competence and problem solving skills which are among the characteristics that promote resitienency, positive development and effective ways of coping.
5. Be more effective than programmes that focus only on transforming information.
6. Be more exciting and rewarding because the content tends to be more realistic and the methods made for and effective than traditional approaches.
7. Promote positive social norms that can impact the broader environment of adolescent health services, schools, staff and families.
8. Assist in development of coping skills that are essential components for healthy development in childhood and adolescence and needed for making a successful transition from childhood to adulthood.

Life Skill Education in Curriculum

Life Skill education needs to be developed as part of as whole instructional initiative designed to support the healthy psychological development of students. Thus improvement of all teachers, principals, other staff members is essential for ensuring a successful and complete roll out of life skill education in the system. The content approach of life skill education focuses on information for increasing knowledge related to specific subject areas. The thematic approaches of life skill education focuses on appropriate themes for the target group are built into the sessions. Life skill learning is facilitated by the use of participatory learning methods and is based on a social learning process. Practice of skills is facilitated by role playing in typical scenarios with a focus on the application of skills and the effect that they have on the outcome of a hypothetical situation. Different combinations of the skills are emphasized depending on the purpose and topic. Life skill education should be designed to enable students to practice skills progressively more demanding situations from low-risk to high-risk situations.

Conclusion: The education system needs to focus on the belief that each student has the innate desire to achieve his maximum potential. Efficient networking of educationists, psychologists, mental health professionals and policy makers would be required to develop a concrete workable life skills training programme. The training programme would need to transcend across all development of stages of the child and should have an in built monitoring and evaluation system. Facilitating the learning of life skills is a central component of programmes designed to promote healthy behavior, mental health and holistic well being. The introduction and form placement of life skills education requires faculty training to promote effective implementation of the programme . In the self management process. Thus life skill education helps in career development, career securing, stress management, time management and developing a positive self concept which leads to a productive, happy and joyous life.

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